

Metal complexes of 1-phenylamino-7-phenyl-4,6-heptadiene-1,3-dione and its Schiff's base

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Abstract : A new type of conjugated β -ketoanilide and its Schiff's base with the keto group attached to olefinic linkage has been synthesized by the reaction of acetoacetanilide and cinnamaldehyde under specified conditions. The existence of these compounds predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol form has been well demonstrated from their IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectral data. Details on the formation of their complexes with Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} and their nature of bonding are discussed on the basis of analytical, IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectral data.

Keywords : Conjugated, β -ketoanilide, Schiff's base, metal complexes, spectra; IR, NMR, mass.

In recent years β -dicarbonyl compounds in which the carbonyl group(s) are directly bonded to olefinic linkage have gained considerable importance¹⁻³ mainly because of the fact that such unsaturated β -dicarbonyls constitute the major biologically active compounds present in several traditional Indian medicinal plants. The best-known example is the curcuminoids, the active chemical constituent of turmeric. Curcuminoids, their synthetic analogues and their metal complexes are known to exhibit anticancer⁴⁻⁹, antioxidant^{6,10,11} and anti-inflammatory^{12,13} activities. The alkenyl linkage appears to be a major factor in determining their biological activities. Therefore, synthesis and characterization of unsaturated compounds having extended conjugation have considerable importance. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of a new conjugated β -dicarbonyl compound, its Schiff's base and their metal complexes.

Results and discussion

The best known method for the synthesis of unsaturated β -dicarbonyls involve the condensation of an aromatic aldehyde with β -dicarbonyl compounds containing at least one acetyl carbonyl function in presence of boric oxide and tri(sec-butyl) borate with *n*-butylamine as the condensing agent¹⁴. The reaction when carried out using cinnamaldehyde and acetoacetanilide yielded two products – unsaturated β -ketoanilide **1** and a Schiff's base **2** formed by the condensation of **1** with *n*-butylamine (Scheme 1) under the

experimental conditions. Details on the synthesis and characterization of these compounds and their typical metal complexes are discussed in this paper.

Scheme 1

Characterization of unsaturated β -ketoanilide (Hbad) and its metal chelates :

The compound is stable, show sharp melting point and is soluble in common organic solvents. Elemental analysis, IR (Table 1), ^1H NMR and mass spectral data of the compound are in agreement with structure 1. The compound

Table 1. Physical, analytical and IR data of the unsaturated β -ketoamide Hbad and its metal chelates

Compd	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)				IR stretching bands (cm ⁻¹)			
			Found (Calcd)				C=O	C=O	C=C	M-O
			C	H	N	M	amide chelated	enolic chelated	alkenyl/phenyl	
Hbad	85	52	78.24 (78.35)	5.80 (5.84)	4.79 (4.81)	-	1678 s	1615 s	1525 m, 1536 m, 1568 m	-
[Ni(bad) ₂]	154	70	71.20 (71.39)	4.98 (5.01)	4.34 (4.38)	9.16 (9.19)	1640 s	1589 s	1518 m, 1544 m, 1579 m	419 m, 492 m
[Cu(bad) ₂]	198	74	70.71 (70.86)	4.96 (4.97)	4.32 (4.35)	9.84 (9.87)	1642 s	1594 s	1518 m, 1548 m, 1581 m	425 m, 470 m
[Zn(bad) ₂]	136	68	70.52 (70.66)	4.91 (4.96)	4.24 (4.34)	10.14 (10.13)	1648 s	1595 s	1515 m, 1544 m, 1583 m	426 m, 650 m
[Cd(bad) ₂]	128	78	65.82 (65.85)	4.58 (4.62)	4.08 (4.04)	15.98 (16.23)	1640 s	1593 s	1519 m, 1538 m, 1578 m	414 m, 492 m

Table 2. Physical, analytical and IR data (cm⁻¹) of the Schiff's base Hbas and its metal chelates

Compd	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)				IR stretching bands (cm ⁻¹)			
			Found (Calcd)				v(C=N)	v(C=O)	C=C	v M-O
			C	H	N	M	chelated	chelated	alkenyl/phenyl	vM-N
Hbas	92	40	79.72 (79.77)	7.49 (7.51)	8.02 (8.09)	-	1640 s	1620 s	1560 m, 1548 m, 1526 m	-
[Ni(bas) ₂]	196	76	72.72 (73.73)	6.54 (6.68)	7.42 (7.48)	7.68 (7.84)	1595 s	1582 s	1564 m, 1548 m, 1528 m	450 m, 528 m
[Cu(bas) ₂]	154	70	72.39 (73.25)	6.54 (6.64)	7.48 (7.43)	8.33 (8.43)	1592 s	1580 s	1560 m, 1554 m, 1524 m	436 m, 532 m
[Zn(bas) ₂]	138	68	72.74 (73.08)	6.52 (6.62)	7.38 (7.41)	8.59 (8.66)	1594 s	1577 s	1558 m, 1546 m, 1525 m	427 m, 531 m
[Cd(bas) ₂]	126	72	68.92 (68.79)	6.19 (6.23)	6.89 (6.98)	13.98 (14.00)	1593 s	1578 s	1574 m, 1538 m, 1526 m	430 m, 527 m

formed well defined and crystalline complexes **3** with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions. The observed C, H, N and metal percentages suggest [M(bad)₂] stoichiometry of the complexes (Table 1). All metal complexes are non-electrolytes in DMF (specific conductance < 10 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) The Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complex showed normal paramagnetic moment.

M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}
3

Infrared spectra The IR spectrum of Hbad is characterized by the presence of two strong bands at 1615 cm⁻¹ and 1678 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of highly conjugated carbonyl and amide carbonyl functions¹⁵. Spectra of the compounds in the region below 1600 cm⁻¹ show several

medium intensity bands due to various C=C and C-N stretching vibrations and to N-H, N-C=O bending, etc. The broad band in the region 3000–3500 cm⁻¹ suggests the existence of the compound predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic form¹⁶. This broad band cleared up in the spectra of metal complexes indicating the replacement of enolic proton by the metal cation during complexation. The bands at 1615 cm⁻¹ and 1678 cm⁻¹ of the free ligand is shifted to ~1590 cm⁻¹ and ~1650 cm⁻¹. This indicates that both the carbonyl groups are involved in coordination with the metal ion. That the carbonyl groups are involved in bonding with the metal as in structure **3** is further supported by the appearance of two medium intensity bands at ~420 cm⁻¹ and ~450 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{M-O}¹⁵. Important bands that appeared in the spectra of complexes are given in Table 1.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectrum of Hbad displayed a one proton singlet at δ 14.1 ppm assignable to the

strong intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic proton¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The NH proton signal is observed at δ 9.5 ppm (broad). The olefinic and methylene proton signals appeared at δ 8 ppm and δ 4 ppm. The aryl proton signals are observed in the range δ 6.8–7.5 ppm. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes the low field enol proton signal of the ligand at δ 14.1 ppm disappeared indicating the replacement of enolic proton by metal cation during complexation. Methine proton singlet and aromatic proton signals shifted slightly to downfield. The resonance signals of alkenyl proton and NH singlet of anilide showed only marginal shifts.

Mass spectra : The formulation of the compound as in structure 1 is clearly supported from the presence of intense molecular ion peak in the mass spectrum at m/z 291. Elimination of OH, CO, C₃H₅O⁺ and C₆H₅NHCO⁺ from the molecular ion which are characteristic of β -dicarbonyl compounds²⁰ is clearly evident from the spectrum. The FAB mass spectrum of the Cu^{II} chelate showed relatively intense (P + 1)⁺ peak corresponding to [Cu(bad)₂] stoichiometry. Peaks due to stepwise removal of aryl groups from the molecular ion, M(bad)⁺, (Hbad)⁺ and fragments of (Hbad)⁺ are also detected in the spectrum. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes. Important fragments appeared in the spectra are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Mass spectral data of β -ketoanilide Hbad, Schiff's base Hbas and their Cu^{II} chelates

Compd.	Mass spectral data (m/z)
Hbad	291, 214, 186, 172, 144, 118, 120, 103, 129, 157, 171, 199
Cu(bad) ₂	645, 643, 553, 551, 461, 459, 332, 330, 291, 203, 201, 171, 157, 129, 103
Hbas	346, 269, 254, 192, 103, 129, 157, 171, 289, 175, 212, 197, 243, 217, 189
Cu(bas) ₂	755, 753, 678, 676, 652, 650, 626, 624, 549, 547, 523, 521, 497, 495, 663, 661, 571, 569, 346, 103, 129

ESR spectra : The ESR spectrum of the copper(II) complex was recorded at 77 K in DMF solution. The observed g and A values (Table 4) are comparable to that reported for copper acetoacetanilide^{21,22}. This suggests the presence of appreciable delocalisation in the chelate ring.

Table 4. ESR parameters of Cu^{II} complexes in DMF at 77 K

Complex	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	$A_{ } \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$A_{\perp} \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Cu(bad) ₂	2.262	2.042	158	44.2
Cu(bas) ₂	2.270	2.060	155	46.0

Electronic spectra : The UV spectrum of the compound showed two absorption maxima, λ_{max} at 386 nm and 280 nm due to various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorptions showed a shift to higher wave

length (~10 nm). In the copper(II) complex the presence of a broad visible band at 15000 cm⁻¹ and the measured μ_{eff} value (1.76 B.M.) support the square-planar structure²³. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at 17800 cm⁻¹ in the visible spectra of the nickel(II) chelate suggest its square planar geometry. In conformity, visible spectrum of the chelate in pyridine solution (10⁻³ M) showed three bands corresponding to configurational change from square planar to octahedral due to the association of pyridine. The three well-separated absorption bands at λ_{max} 8234, 13556 and 24349 cm⁻¹ correspond to the transitions ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P), respectively.

Characterization of the Schiff's base (Hbas) and its metal complexes : The second product 2 obtained was characterized as a Schiff's base formed by the condensation of *n*-butylamine with Hbad on the basis of elemental analysis (Table 2), molecular weight determination and spectral data.

The Schiff's base formed well defined and crystalline complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions. The observed C, H, N and metal percentages suggest [M(bas)₂] stoichiometry (Table 2). The complexes behave as non-electrolytes in dmf (specific conductance < 10 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in 10⁻³ M solution) and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for the preparation. Magnetic moment measurements show that Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complex showed normal paramagnetic moment. IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data are in agreement with the structure 4 of the complexes.

Infrared spectra : That the amide carbonyl of 1 has involved in the Schiff's base formation is clearly indicated in the IR spectrum of Hbas. Thus the band at 1678 cm⁻¹ is absent in the spectrum and further no absorption band exist in the 1650–1800 cm⁻¹ region. The spectrum of the compound in the region 1600–1650 cm⁻¹ show two prominent bands at 1620 cm⁻¹ and 1640 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching of enolised conjugated carbonyl and azomethine (C=N) group²⁴. That strong intramolecular hydrogen bond as in structure 2 exist in the compound is clearly indicated from the presence of the broad band in the region 2800–3500 cm⁻¹. In the spectra of metal complexes both the bands in the region 1600–1650

cm^{-1} disappeared and instead two prominent bands appeared at $\sim 1595 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to metal-bonded C=O and C=N groups²⁵ in addition to various alkenyl and aromatic C=C stretching frequencies that appeared in the range $1525\text{--}1565 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the free ligand. The broad absorption of the ligand in the region $2800\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ cleared up in the spectra of metal complexes indicating the replacement of enolic proton by metal cation during complexation. A medium intensity band at $\sim 2900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ appeared due to NH stretching vibration. In accordance with this observation the new bands appeared at ~ 450 and $\sim 530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to M–O and M–N stretching frequencies¹⁵. The characteristic IR bands and their probable assignments are given in Table 2.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectrum of Hbas displayed two signals in the low field at δ 11.43 ppm and δ 9.4 ppm assignable to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol and the NH protons^{17–19}. Other signals observed in the spectrum fully agree with the structure 2. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes the low field enolic proton singlet at δ 11.43 ppm of the free ligand disappeared and the NH proton signal slightly shifted to low field. The assignment of various signals fully support the mode of coordination and the formulation of the complex as in structure 4.

Mass spectra : The compound showed intense molecular ion peak at m/z 346 corresponding to the molecular formula of the compound. The FAB mass spectrum of its Cu^{II} chelate shows the stepwise removal of the aryl and alkenyl groups. Molecular ion peak, fragments due to M(bas)⁺ and (Hbas)⁺ are also detected in the spectrum. A number of fragments containing copper in agreement with the natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes are also present in the spectrum (Table 3).

ESR spectra : The ESR spectrum of the copper(II) complex was recorded at 77 K in DMF solution. The observed g and A values (Table 4) suggest the presence of appreciable delocalisation in the chelate ring^{21,22}.

Electronic spectra : The UV spectrum of Hbas showed two broad absorption bands with λ_{max} at 275 nm and 370 nm assignable to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The spectra of the complexes show close similarity with the ligand which indicate that no structural alteration of the ligand has occurred during complexation. In the copper(II) complex the presence of a broad visible band at 15000 cm^{-1} and the measured μ_{eff} value (1.77 B.M.) support the square-planar structure²³. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at $\sim 17800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the visible spec-

trum of the nickel(II) chelate suggest its square planar geometry. In conformity, the visible spectrum of the chelate in pyridine solution ($10^{-3} M$) showed three bands corresponding to configuration change from square planar to octahedral due to the association of pyridine. The three well-separated absorption bands at λ_{max} 8034, 13552 and 24352 cm^{-1} correspond to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$; ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively.

Antifungal studies : Unsaturated β -dicarbonyl compounds such as curcuminoids are known to possess antifungal and antimicrobial activities in addition to their numerous biological significance^{2–11}. Since the unsaturated β -ketoanilide is structurally related to curcuminoids, the antifungal activity of the compound and their typical metal complexes were also studied by the disk diffusion method. The three different fungal strains used are *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus parasiticus* and *Rhizopus oryzae*²⁶. The results reveal that the compounds possess significant activity against all the tested organism and the free ligands exhibited more activity than their metal complexes.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by micro analyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) at CDRI, Lucknow and metal contents by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in methanol solution ($10^{-4} M$) on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr discs) on a 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer, ESR spectra (X-band) at 77 K using a Varian E 112 ESR spectrometer and mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at $28 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using solution of about $10^{-3} M$ concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of conjugated β -ketoanilide and its Schiff's base : Acetoacetanilide (0.01 mol, 1.77 g) was stirred for ~ 1 h with boric oxide (0.0035 mol, 0.25 g) to obtain acetoacetanilide-boron complex. To this reaction mixture cinnamaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.37 g), dissolved in dry ethylacetate (5 mL) containing tri(*sec*-butyl)borate (0.002 mol, 4.6 g) was added. The mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer and while stirring *n*-butylamine (0.5 mL dissolved in 5 mL dry ethylacetate) was added during 30 min. Stirring was continued for an additional period of ~ 5 h and the solution were kept aside overnight. Hot ($\sim 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) hydro-

chloric acid (0.1 M, 10 mL) was added and the mixture again stirred for ~1 h. The organic layer separated was extracted with ethylacetate. The combined extract were evaporated to dryness and the residual paste was stirred with HCl (0.1 N, 25 mL) for ~1 h. It was then kept aside overnight. The solid product separated was collected, washed with water and dried in vacuum. When the product obtained was subjected to tlc, two distinct spots were obtained. They were separated quantitatively by column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh) as detailed below.

The product was dissolved in minimum amount of ethylacetate and placed over the column (2 × 200 cm) densely packed with silica gel. The eluting solvent used was 1 : 2 acetone-chloroform mixture. As the elution proceeds two bands were developed in the column, a bright yellow lower band and an orange red upper band. The lower region was collected as 10 mL aliquots in separate tubes and in each case, the homogeneity was established by tlc. The elution was then continued using 1 : 3 mixture of chloroform and acetone to recover the orange red upper band. The two compounds isolated were recrystallised from hot benzene to give spectroscopically pure materials. Analytical and spectral data of the compounds eluted first from chromatographic column conform to the conjugated β -ketoanilide 1 and second to the Schiff's base 2.

Synthesis of metal complexes of conjugated β -ketoanilide. An ethanolic solution of the metal salt (0.001 mol, 20 mL) was added slowly with stirring to a solution of the compound in methanol (0.002 mol, 25 mL). The mixture was stirred well and sodium acetate was added to keep the pH around 6. It was then refluxed gently for ~3 h and concentrated to half the original volume. On cooling to room temperature the complex gets precipitated. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with 1 : 1 methanol-water mixture and dried. For purity, the complexes were recrystallised from hot chloroform.

Synthesis of metal complexes of Schiff's base : To a refluxing solution of the compound in ethanol (0.002 mol, 20 mL) an aqueous solution of metal acetate (0.001 mol, 15 mL) was added drop by drop with stirring. The pH of the solution was adjusted around 6 using sodium acetate and refluxing was continued for ~2 h. The solution was concentrated to half the volume. It was then cooled in ice and the

precipitated complex was filtered, washed several times with water, then with ethanol and recrystallised from hot benzene.

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